

ACTIVITY REPORT (June 1, 2024 - November 15, 2025).

Open Culture Business Models for Cultural Heritage Management: An Investigation of Italian State Museums

Young Researchers Grant

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1. SUMMARY

The project “Open Culture Business Models for Cultural Heritage Management: An Investigation of Italian State Museums” (P.I. Dore), promoted and funded by iNEST under the Young Researchers (YR) calls, was closely aligned with the main research lines and activities of iNEST, in which the P.I. was involved, encompassing three of the four sub-RTs of RT3: RT3.1 Sustainable experience design for the circular economy in the heritage city and for accessible, diverse, and inclusive places; RT3.3 Sustainable business model design for the sharing and community-based economy of places; and RT3.4 Culture and creative regeneration of natural and built environments for the sustainable development of places.. The funding enabled the development of high-impact, interdisciplinary research at the intersection of law and management, with a focus on open and inclusive culture, sustainable governance and business models for museums.

The project contributed to strengthening expertise in cultural management and fostering new methodological skills of law & management. The research was consolidated through active participation in scientific societies and national and international conferences, promoting stable interdisciplinary collaborations and recognized positioning within academic and institutional arenas on open culture. In this context, particular relevance was given to participation in European discussion forums, including those of the European Commission and the European Parliament. In addition to delivering relevant scientific outputs, the project provided opportunities for coordination and project management, including addressing and mitigating unforeseen risks, reorganizing priorities, reallocating resources, and ensuring compliance with critical deadlines and reporting obligations.

2. PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the project was carried out in accordance with the work plan defined in the proposal, ensuring alignment with the planned tasks, milestones, and deliverables over the project duration. Research activities combined doctrinal and comparative legal analysis with

management-oriented approaches, and were complemented by empirical investigation, including case studies, fieldwork, and stakeholder engagement within the iNEST ecosystem. The project was structured around three main tasks.

The first task was devoted to providing the theoretical framework, through a comprehensive literature review on Open Culture Business Model Canvases as applied to the museum sector, and a desk-based analysis of the institutional and regulatory setting governing Italian state museums. This phase led to the identification of the key elements for the design of the Open Culture Business Model Canvas (OCBMC) and the selection of the pilot museums to be investigated. The second task focused on developing the business model canvas, combining primary data gathered through focus group discussions with practitioners and stakeholders and an online survey administered to Italian museum managers, with secondary data drawn from financial and administrative documents of state museums with special autonomy. An interim workshop was organised to share preliminary findings and gather feedback from the relevant scientific and stakeholder communities. The third task was dedicated to testing and validating the OCBMC through direct observations in the pilot museums selected from the iNEST territory, followed by the organisation of the project's final conference to present the research outputs and explore the wider applicability of the findings beyond the state museum context.

During the project, an unforeseen circumstance significantly affected its implementation. The research fellow who was part of the original team left the university before the conclusion of the project, leaving the P.I. as the sole person responsible for carrying out all research activities. This unexpected change in the composition of the research team inevitably resulted in delays in the execution of several planned activities, as tasks originally distributed between two researchers had to be absorbed and managed by a single person, also with the support of the main P.I. of iNEST SP6 RT3. Notwithstanding these difficulties, the P.I. continued to pursue the project's objectives with commitment, adapting the implementation timeline where necessary while preserving the scientific integrity and overall coherence of the research.

The achievement of project objectives was monitored through the delivery of scientific articles and other research outputs. Additionally, the organisation of scientific events, as well as the dissemination and public engagement activities were carried out in collaboration with leading organisations in the museum field, for instance, the International Committee of Museums (ICOM) and ICOM Italia, and through active involvement in the iNEST cross-cutting activities CC2 and CC3. Overall, and despite the challenges encountered, the project achieved a high level of coherence between planned activities, expected outputs, and actual results, contributing to both scientific excellence and the broader impact objectives of the PNRR and the iNEST ecosystem.

In addition, administrative and project management activities were carried out to support the overall coordination of RT3. These activities ensured compliance with project milestones and PNRR deadlines, including the preparation and submission of periodic reports, monitoring of research and dissemination activities, and mapping of administrative and decision-making processes.

2.1 Open Culture and museum management: from business models to regenerative development

The project examined the relationship between copyright law and cultural heritage law, with particular attention to policies on reproducing images of works and museum collections, to assess their consistency with market dynamics and the safeguarding of the right to culture. In parallel, a systematic study was conducted on open access policies and strategies, investigating both the regulatory limitations and the potential for openness (open culture) in the sharing and reuse of cultural resources. The analysis addressed in detail the challenges posed by legal uncertainty and resistance to managerial change. Further investigation focused on accessibility and inclusion policies, carried out in collaboration with Italian and international cultural institutions and research centres.

The preliminary results of the project suggested to broaden the scope of the analysis to the extent of including non-state museums insofar as they were in the iNEST territory. This allowed to investigate the intangible and immaterial barriers that hinder the full valorisation of cultural heritage in more museums. Its aim was to reconstruct and rethink the blueprint of open culture in Italian museums, while adopting a transnational and comparative perspective. To this end, the iNEST research assumptions on open culture were tested also from a comparative perspective, e.g. in Indigenous culture museums in Australia, where the tension between openness and closure is remarkable.

The main findings highlighted a complex and generally restrictive framework, sharply contrasting with European policies promoting openness, and underscoring the need for reform interventions. These results contributed to the European debate on copyright reform and access to cultural heritage and were published in high-ranking international journals and other outlets.

The results confirmed the strong tension between forces of openness and closure already identified in the literature, highlighting the opportunity to experiment with alternative management models and to define an interdisciplinary law & management theoretical framework. This was further validated and applied using quantitative approaches, based on data collected through a specific survey administered through the services of the company SWG. Additionally, this established the conditions for a unique collaboration in the upcoming national ISTAT survey “Indagine sui musei e le istituzioni similari”. For this purpose, together with the iNEST SP6 RT3 P.I. Prof. Della Lucia and ISTAT researchers, the Y.R. P.I. contributed to enhance the ISTAT initial draft with specific sections addressing digitalization, accessibility, and inclusion in Italian museums.

In line with the YR project's scope, the research explored the themes of cultural regeneration and placemaking, examining the role of intellectual property in the enhancement of territories and shared heritage, with particular attention to the risks of drifting toward rigid, exclusive models that limit public access. These issues were investigated through field studies conducted in close collaboration with stakeholders within the iNEST ecosystem, such as Castel Campo (Fiavè, Trento) and the Museo Etnografico del Trentino METS (S. Michele all'Adige, Trento). The findings connected legal reflections on intellectual property rights with the

processes of regenerating natural and built environments, contributing to a critical understanding of territorial branding strategies and local development dynamics. These results have been published as chapters in international volumes addressing intellectual property, heritage, placemaking, cultural regeneration, and sustainable territorial development.

3. RESEARCH OUTPUTS

The research outcomes encompass scientific publications, the organization and moderation of conferences and research seminars, as well as the preparation of new project proposals aimed at consolidating and further developing the results achieved. The scientific output includes the following publications:

1. Dore, G., & Arisi, M. (Eds.). (2024). Open up museums! Prospects and challenges of accessibility, diversity and inclusion. Ledizioni (OA). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281624>. ISBN print: 9791256000296.
2. Dore, G. (2024). Reading “open museums” through a copyright lens: A primer on evidence-based legal research. In G. Dore & M. Arisi (Eds.), Open up museums! Prospects and challenges of accessibility, diversity and inclusion (pp. 121-132). Ledizioni. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281624>. ISBN print: 9791256000296.
3. Della Lucia, M., Dore, G., & Umar, M. (2024). Cultural heritage management in museums: The open culture dilemma. In Management of sustainability and well-being for individuals and society: Proceedings of the Sinergie-SIMA Management Conference 2024. Parma, June 13-14, 2024 (pp. 1137-1141). <https://www.sijmsima.it/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/SHORT-PAPER-CONFERECE-PROCEEDING-PARMA-2024-1.pdf>. ISBN: 9788894713657.
4. Della Lucia, M., & Dore, G. (2025). Open culture and indigenous heritage: pathways to sustainable management. In L. Ruhanen (Ed.), & CAUTHE. 35th CAUTHE Conference Proceedings: Transforming Tomorrow: Leveraging Opportunities to Create Change in Tourism, Hospitality and Events. Council for Australian University Tourism and Hospitality Education. Brisbane, Qld., February 10-13, 2025 (n. 52). <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.9780645938111>. ISBN: 9780645938111.
5. Della Lucia, M., Dore G., & Tamma M. (2025). Professional Development in Museum Education: Insights from a Multi-Case Analysis. In N. Abidi, S. Cardinali, S., D. Johnson, D. (Eds.). Proceedings of the 19th International Conference of the Academy of Global Business Research and Practice (AGBRP). Sustainability: Perspectives of Policy, Business, Technology, AI, and Education. Dubai, January 8-10, 2025 (pp. 53-62). https://www.agbrp.world/_files/ugd/5793fb_cb118964ae3f4c509f09c48f44dc3744.pdf. ISBN: 9798987670125.
6. Della Lucia, M., Dore, G., Lazic, S., & Clerici, M. (in press, 2026). Rethinking cultural heritage in placemaking: From preservation to regenerative development in Castel Campo. In M. Della Lucia et al. (Eds.), Sustainable business models: Insights from the tourism, cultural and creative sectors. Emerald. ISBN print: 9781805926740.

7. Dore, G. (in press, 2026). Potential conflicts between the protection of cultural heritage and intellectual property. In I. Stamatoudi, A. Zervaki, & M. Shehade (Eds.), Elgar Encyclopaedia of Art and Cultural Heritage Law. Edward Elgar. ISBN: 9782807937000.
8. Iljadica, M., Oruc, P., Dore, G., et al. (in press, 2026). City™© place branding and intellectual property law. In S. Kheria & J. Kanellopoulou (Eds.), Legal geographies of intellectual property. Edward Elgar.

Additionally, the following paper and presentation were delivered during international and national scientific meetings:

1. Dore, G. (2024, 18 Dec). La condivisione del patrimonio culturale in Italia: Limiti normativi e prospettive di apertura. Il diritto d'autore nella prospettiva della scienza aperta e della valorizzazione del patrimonio culturale, National Research Council (CNR), Rome, Italia.
2. Dore, G. (2024, 17 Jun). Opere d'arte visive e riproduzione: I nuovi scenari offerti dall'attuazione della direttiva europea sul diritto d'autore. Fotografia e diritto d'autore: Prospettive e scenari futuri nella società dell'informazione, Salerno, Italia (online).
3. Dore, G. (2024, 20 Dec). All square? Questioning the efficiency of image reproduction policies in Italian state museums. Società Italiana di Diritto e Economia (SIDE) Annual Conference, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italia.
4. Dore, G. (2024, 6 Jun). Advancing professional development in the museum educational landscape: A law & management perspective. MIC2024: Next Generation Challenges. Innovation, Regeneration and Inclusion, University of Trento, Trento, Italia.
5. Dore, G. (2024, 2 Jul). Market culture and trade mark law: Enhancement, preservation, or privatisation of heritage? ATRIP Annual Conference, Rome, Italia.
6. Dore, G. (2024, 17 Oct). Designing business model canvas for open culture management. AVICOM Annual Conference: News from the Digital Museum World, Turin, Italia (online).
7. Dore, G. (2025, 12 Jun). A magic mirror for the Vitruvian tale: Controlled images, frozen rights, and illusory gains. Botticelli v. Warhol: Comparative Perspectives on the Use of Cultural Heritage Images, Florence, Italia.
8. Dore, G. (2025, 25 Sep). City™© place branding and intellectual property law. 10th Advances in Tourism Marketing Conference (ATMC): Resilient Futures & Creative Placemaking, Heraklion, Grecia.
9. Dore, G. (2025, 11 Oct). Learning about the critical interplay between copyright and generative AI through university policies. EIPTN Worldwide Annual Conference 2025: IP in the Era of Geopolitical, Technological, and Fundamental Rights Challenges, Portsmouth, Regno Unito.

Furthermore, the YR project contributed to the organisation and moderation of the following conferences and seminars:

1. International conference “MIC2024: Next Generation Challenges. Innovation, Regeneration and Inclusion”, Università di Trento, 5-8 giugno 2024, <https://webmagazine.unitn.it/evento/economia/120928/mic2024>. Scientific committee (among others): M. Della Lucia, G. Dore (UniTrento DEM).
2. Seminar “Planning for placemaking. Regulating works of architecture in tourism and regeneration projects”. Relatrice: Dr. Marta Iljadica, CREATE Centre for Regulation of the Creative Economy, University of Glasgow. DEM, 10 aprile 2025. Scientific committee: M. Della Lucia, G. Dore (UniTrento DEM).
3. Seminar “Human Factor in European Museums’ Intellectual Property Management through Sociocultural, Legal, Political and Economic Determinants”. Relatore: Dr. Konrad Gliściński, Jagiellonian University (Kraków). DEM, 16 maggio 2025. Scientific committee: M. Della Lucia, G. Dore (UniTrento DEM).

Finally, in line with the PNRR project’s impact and dissemination objectives, significant and diverse public engagement activities were carried out at the local level, including public events, outreach, and professional training. To maximize impact both within and beyond the iNEST ecosystem, these initiatives were implemented in connection with the transversal iNEST CC3 Citizen Engagement activities and in collaboration with local, national, and international projects focused on accessibility and open culture.

The YR project was central to the organization and moderation of free, public events carried out in synergy with cultural institutions, including museums and music conservatories, and in collaboration with scholars, professionals, and representatives of organizations active in the cultural and creative sectors. These initiatives were specifically aimed at fostering constructive dialogue on the iNEST research results concerning sustainable business models in the cultural sector. On multiple occasions, the events included opportunities for participation and co-design of experiences through interactive formats, supported by art-based tools drawn from prose, theatre, and the visual arts:

1. International symposium “Museums as Public Spaces and Agents of Social Change”. Filarmonica di Trento, June 6, 2024, https://webmagazine.unitn.it/fileswebmagazine/download/120851/037224inestmuseia3web_0.pdf. The event, organized within the framework of the international conference MIC2024 and under the patronage of ICOM Italia, promoted a critical reflection on the contemporary role of museums, not only as places of preservation, but above all as public spaces capable of catalyzing innovation, cultural regeneration, and social inclusion, with implications for territorial sustainability and active citizen engagement. Scientific committee: M. Della Lucia, G. Dore, A. Montresor (University of Trento), M.C. Pedicchio, F. Borza (University of Trieste). Participating museums: Museo di Castelvecchio (Verona); University Museums of Padua; MART (Trento); MUSE (Trento); Museion (Bolzano); Natural History Museum (Verona); Immaginario Scientifico (Trieste).

2. Conference and laboratory “Open Museums: Incontri e Partenze al Crocevia”, METS, San Michele all’Adige, May 26, 2025, <https://www.museosanmichele.it/dettaglio-appuntamento/-/d/open-museums>. The event was co-organized with METS, under the patronage of ICOM Italia, within the framework of the iNEST project and the PRIN 2022 project “*sMArT cities CHallenges and opportunities: a participatory approach to the design of sustainable, creative and connected cities*” (coordinated by Prof. Maria Della Lucia). The presentation of the volume *Open Up Museums!* (edited by G. Dore and M. Arisi, Ledizioni, 2024) provided an opportunity to introduce the narrative of the open and inclusive museum and to activate an experiential workshop focused on spaces, senses, stories, and symbols. The initiative encouraged reflection on the role of museums as open cultural infrastructures, capable of fostering dialogue and co-design among communities, territories, and ecosystems. Scientific committee: M. Della Lucia, G. Dore, S. Lazic (University of Trento), A. Tomasi, D. Finardi, A. Santoro (METS). Participating museums: METS; MUSE; MART. Other stakeholders involved: Natourism (Trento); HIT - Hub Innovazione Trentino.

The YR project also played a key role in outreach activities aimed at making the research topics and results accessible and understandable to a broad and diverse public, fostering dialogue between universities, cultural institutions, and civil society. Within this framework, the episode “Quite FAIR. Senza accesso non c’è ricerca” was conceived and produced, exploring the complex interdependence between data and research, for the podcast *Aperto: Accessibilità digitale per il patrimonio culturale*, curated by Iolanda Pensa for the Scuola nazionale del patrimonio e delle attività culturali. The episode was recorded in Milan (Studio Storie Avvolgibili) and distributed across multiple platforms: Spotify link.

4. BUDGET IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the project budget was carried out in accordance with the financial guidelines and reporting requirements of the PNRR and iNEST framework, and in line with the expenditure categories approved in the budget section of the project proposal. Resources were allocated efficiently across the four main cost items foreseen therein.

Attention was given to ensuring consistency between the planned budget structure and the achievement of project milestones, as well as to the timely and justified reallocation of resources in response to emerging needs, within the limits of the approved budget. Expenditure on specialist consultancy services for data collection and analysis supported the empirical component of the research by enabling the engagement of a market research company, thus ensuring the rigour and quality of the data gathering and analytical processes. Costs associated with open access publications, covering article processing charges and proofreading services, ensured broad and timely dissemination of results in line with Open Science standards and protocols. Resources allocated to the organisation of scientific events funded the interim workshop and the final conference, including speaker travel, translation, technical support, and communication materials, thereby maximising the project’s scientific impact and outreach.

Finally, expenditure on participation in scientific events and fieldwork activities covered research field trips to selected pilot museums and travel costs for attendance at national and international conferences, supporting both the empirical investigation and the project's visibility within the broader scientific community.

All financial activities were conducted in full compliance with reporting obligations, ensuring transparency, traceability, and alignment with both the approved budget and the expected outcomes of the project.

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YR P.I.

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DISCLAIMER

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